

THE ACTUAL PROBLEM OF MUSIC ART AND STUDENTS' INTEREST IN IT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8387548>

Abstract. *It is known that the art of music, according to its upbringing, vividly describes people's lives, their attitude to reality and various inner experiences through musical sounds and artistic images. Music is an important source of education with the ability to strongly influence human emotions. The earlier the influence of the art of music begins on children and adolescents, the easier it is to achieve the desired goal.*

Keywords: *musical art, music lessons, students, concept of art and culture, national cultural heritage, folklore, introducing students to masterpieces of art, spiritual values, musical consciousness.*

In the life we live, the art of music does not leave us from childhood. The only thing that matters is how we use the music. Acquainting students with: broadcasts, TV shows, films about writers, lyricists and composers plays a special role in determining their inclinations and directing their interests to creative films. In particular, in group classes: articles, poems, stories, conducting conversations about works of different genres, in turn, helps to ensure cohesion between common topics in music lessons.

As we mentioned above, the art of music vividly describes the life of people, their unique attitudes and various inner experiences through musical sounds and artistic images. Music is an important source of education due to its ability to strongly influence human emotions through the art of music. The earlier the ability to perceive the art of music begins in children and adolescents, the easier it is to achieve the intended goal. Our work experience, and the opinion of our qualified teachers and trainers: It is much more difficult to master what was lost in childhood in adulthood. If works of art reach the heart of the young child through the best means, if he feels the influence of the colors of sounds on the human emotions, he will rise to a cultural level that cannot be reached by any other influence. The art of music that we live does not leave us from childhood. Only in what way should we use what kind of music, our students should be able to distinguish correctly. In order to answer these questions correctly, we asked our teachers the following questions:

Dear children, what songs and works of art do you love to listen to and listen to?

1. Dear children, which song you chose in music class and the content of the works you read, do you consider to be an example and example for you in the future when you become a mature person?

If we look at the history, Arina Radionova, the nanny of A.S.Pushkin, did not set herself the goal of Pushkin becoming a great poet, she only told him various fairy tales and songs. As a result of these things, as we have seen, he found a great place in being a poet. In this regard, we ask ourselves our national anthem? What songs did our sisters and grandmothers sing to us? Who can remember these now? Today, no matter how busy our parents are, it would be good if they did not spare time for their children, but paid special attention to their musical education. The reason

is that, unfortunately, nowadays, our observation shows that various audio players of information communication tools have entered the lives of children.

This is a natural point. But it's a pity that young people don't know their folklore and art, they don't realize that there are bright images in national tunes through artistic images, today's youth should be able to understand the best songs and words of our national heritage, and they should be able to learn the good qualities of the heroes of our history.

There is a saying in our people: "A bird does what it sees in its nest". It means every child receives the first education from his parents, family members, and close people around him. A positive atmosphere in the family, mutual relations of family members, respect and attention to each other, kindness, mutual support and their relationship to music, literature play a key role in the development of children's initial concepts and skills. Children's personality is formed in the course of their activities. The activity of the student is already very interesting, uniquely beautiful and colorful in terms of form. Only when these various qualities become a constant need characteristic of children, their activity will increase. This beautiful feeling, which gives pleasure and spiritual pleasure, has a strong influence on the education of children and students, especially the sophistication. Therefore, the cultural, artistic and aesthetic upbringing of a child prepares a thorough ground for important spiritual beauty. Based on our pedagogical observations and our own experience, we came to the conclusion that it is necessary to pay special attention to work with parents' meetings of students. For example: what conditions should be created at home to attract children to music at parent meetings? Students should have conditions at home so that children will be more interested in music and literature lessons, and their passion for art will reach the level of full inclusion of children's creative powers. Through various musical ideas, children acquire the musical language of various streams, learn to understand the art of music, learn to express it, and master music notation. All this expands the worldview of children and adolescents and enriches their worldview. Thus, the influence of the art of music on a person can be realized through various methods. These are:

- a) Listening to music
- b) Through execution
- c) Mastering music recording
- d) Procedures for promoting and promoting the art of music, etc.

All the above-mentioned methods play an important role in the formation of musical aesthetic education of children. Enriches their musical culture. Thus, we tried to show the psychological and social mechanisms related to the actual problems of applying the interdisciplinary integration of music and literature lessons in the process of musical aesthetic education in the research of the theory of musical influence on young students, taking into account the problems existing today based on the system of musical aesthetic education of children.

It can be seen that musical-educational work is a component of aesthetic education, and it is important to further improve the education of students' feelings, taste and perception.

Pedagogical process in the most basic activities of music lessons requires students to be integrated in their practical performance skills in harmony and at a certain level of stable listening. This is especially evident in singing activities. To achieve pure unison in singing, to tune, to accompany, to achieve ensemble, to achieve that the whole class group (choir) perform works of various complexity as a "whole organism" and to bring the students' musical abilities to the

maximum. Children whose musical abilities are not well developed will have "slow" musical learning. This has a negative effect on the weakening of musical hearing and musical memory.

For this reason, it is necessary to organize possible pedagogical activities to bring out the hidden abilities of students in order to form their abilities. Well-known pedagogues and psychologists evaluate ability as a unique feature of human personality and consider it in connection with certain activities, and believe that without appropriate activity, ability may not exist or develop at all. This situation can be clearly seen in the direction of music. We use the phrase "talented" when we evaluate the musical talent of some students. We use the term "disabled" to refer to students who do not have a good voice and cannot express their thoughts meaningfully. Ability and inability depend on many psychological and physiological factors of the formation of the child's personality. Heredity, family environment, the environment in which the child grew up, and social conditions play an important role in this. It is impossible for a human being to be completely "incompetent". Every person has the ability to one degree or another. Each person manifests this quality in different ways. Inability to show one's ability well can also be related to the result of a person's psychological state (excitement, confusion, lack of self-confidence). In such situations, the teacher-pedagogue should try to bring out the hidden abilities of the child's personality. When the hidden abilities of a person are considered as his unique characteristics, these characteristics become the basis for his further development, that is, the development of his musical ability. The development of abilities depends on how the teacher manages and organizes the educational process, as well as on his pedagogical approach to each child individually.

Often, lessons are conducted at a level that does not develop musical abilities, or even hinders their development. This is often observed in teachers who do not have sufficient knowledge and experience in music pedagogy and methodology. In the educational process, it is necessary to learn and know the individual characteristics of the child in order to choose the forms of work, methods and tools that help the child to develop his musical abilities, and to use them skillfully.

When analyzing the problem of musical abilities, first of all, it should be said that they consist of a wide set of qualities that are interrelated and cannot be separated from each other. If any of these features are "passive" in the educational process, this indicates that the child has not been able to show his abilities well or that his "abilities" have not been developed in this direction. In such cases, the music teacher should thoroughly study each child's musical abilities and record changes in them in a special notebook. Accordingly, working with children individually or in groups of different levels is one of the most effective forms of work. Without denying the ability given by nature, it is permissible to say that every physically healthy child can develop musical perception, musical hearing, and performance ability. In this process, it is not the child's genetics or natural ability, but the teacher's professional skills, the methodology used in the lesson that is important.

Musical ability is explained by the fact that young students have developed more musical hearing. Memory, perception, imagination and attention are in a person, and a person who has this ability can quickly and easily learn musical tone, tonality, and methods from a young age.

Those with comparative ability are mainly distinguished by their inability to clearly identify the tonality of the piece of music they have heard. In most cases, one of the most difficult skills in music lessons is the fact that some students do not have a well-developed absolute hearing

ability. Such children create serious difficulties for the teacher especially during singing. The fact that their voice does not harmonize with the music and the ensemble (does not fall into tune) has a negative effect on the collective performance.

Musical hearing is made up of external hearing and internal hearing, and external hearing is the ability to receive music that is heard, and internal hearing is the ability to think and be affected by music as if seeing and hearing music.

These are related to very complex psychological factors, and sometimes people overestimate their own abilities. Also, there are cases of failure to show during the lesson. This can be caused by shyness of some people (students), being "slow" in front of many people, shyness, lack of self-confidence. In such situations, it is important for music teachers to be high-level psychologist-pedagogues along with pedagogy. It is important for the teacher to study each child carefully individually, to identify their abilities, to realize them, to work using appropriate methods and tools, to educate the teacher's sense of self-confidence, to encourage it, and to repeat it on stage and in front of many people. Interest, in turn, causes children to learn it, singing, theoretical and practical performance skills and skills to increase their desire and motivation. It is these factors that effectively influence the process of formation of their musical abilities.

While conducting music lessons, the teacher should undertake the following tasks in order to meaningfully and effectively implement musical education.

1. To make children love and interest in music;
2. Education of students in singing, reading music and vocal-choir skills;
3. Developing students' creative abilities;
4. Teaching to sing songs expressively;
5. To enrich the theoretical and practical knowledge of music;

Implementation of these tasks effectively affects the development of students' musical abilities.

Children at this age begin to transition from childhood to adulthood, and therefore consider this period as a transitional period. They now start acting like adults and want to be addressed as adults. At the same time, there are cases where they overestimate their mental and physical capabilities. Especially in the 6th grade, children finally get excited and want to express their opinion about everything, most of them are responsive and generous. Sometimes teachers find it difficult to manage 6-7 graders. They don't like being overly demanding and putting them in order, and on the contrary, letting them have their way will make them nervous.

One of the important aspects is that they start to think independently and look at everything with a critical eye.

Intensive growth occurs in students aged 5-7. They begin to mature quickly psychophysiologicaly. They grow taller, their bones begin to grow, and they develop better mentally. They are also now showing signs of puberty. They try to do what they say. If they don't say it, they will quickly become angry.

Importantly, at this age, that is, at the age of 13-15, an important biological change, that is, a state of mutation, occurs. The state of mutation directly depends on the vocal apparatus of the students, the vocal cords are sharply stretched and thickened. This condition is especially noticeable in boys. As boys' vocal cords lengthen and thicken dramatically, they now develop a new, raspy, masculine voice. During the 6th-7th grade, they have two voices.

First, sometimes their small childish voice dominates, and sometimes their newly formed masculine voice dominates. Such cases of voice change make it difficult for them to find their own voice and sing.

A music teacher should anticipate this situation and allow them to find their exact voice. Some experts say that 6-7 graders should not be taught songs. But most practicing teachers say that it is necessary to help children of this age to get used to a new voice and to develop their singing skills in a new voice.

Taking into account the changes that occur in children, laryngology doctors also work in each school. They check and monitor the changes in the throat.

The music teacher, in consultation with the laryngologist, may sometimes allow the student not to sing. It is necessary not to sing, especially when there is a sharp change in the voice, when there are elements of tension and redness in the throat.

In boys, in a short period of time, the vocal cords are doubled and thickened. This causes an octave drop in their voice.

Before the mutation, children's voices sang in the interval from the small octave "si" (H) to the second octave "re-mi-fa" (D,E,F), but due to the mutation, they now sing in the interval from the note of the big octave "la, si" (A,H) to the notes of the first octave "re-mi-fa" (D,E,F).

When a new voice is formed, it is necessary not to allow tension in children's voice. Because the vocal cords and ligaments are not yet well formed, they are delicate and fragile. It will be necessary to shout loudly, to keep them from eating hot and cold food one after the other, and to warn them about this regularly.

Usually children of this age shout at the top of their voices to call each other, shout out their emotions and try to sing louder than everyone else when they sing.

13-15-year-old girls also have the mutation. But there are no signs of rasping in their voice. The vocal cords and membranes do not grow as fast as boys. Only 10-15 percent grow and the vocal cords thicken. Due to this, the change in their sound is almost imperceptible. Only in their voices, the majesty of adults begins to be felt.

It is recommended to do special work on keeping their voice, regardless of the changes. Sometimes you can feel their temperature rise. In such cases, it is necessary to be content with freeing them to sing and watching others carefully.

It is necessary to rely on the advice of a laryngologist to determine how the changes that occur due to puberty are taking place. Sometimes it is necessary to rely on the advice of a laryngologist. Sometimes laryngologists have the right to give instructions about the need to release them from singing.

In 5-7th grade students, mental development is also noticeable. They will now be able to help the teacher to observe freedom in the classroom, take care of the flowers and establish order in the classroom during the lesson.

In the process of systematically singing as a team, they notice how well the teacher's requirements are being met. They learn the structure of intervals and chords and different scales given by music theory. They can talk about composers in detail. They can find out the idea of musical works, and give characteristics of sound character by looking at their timbres.

Pupils of this age can also perceive different actions well. They are also able to perform various actions on how to position themselves on the stage.

Conducting 2/3; 3/4; 4/4 to students taking into account these possibilities can also be assigned. They now also begin to feel the responsibility of conducting themselves in front of the students as conductors.

All students express their desire to conduct the class choir. The teacher should try to find a way to satisfy their wishes.

The process of listening to music allows students to form their imaginations. As a result of getting used to listening to the content of the music, they try to imagine the reality of the piece through their own imagination. In such cases, the teacher should be able to allow each student to think freely and create conditions for independent thinking. In this way, they are taught from concrete thinking to abstract thinking. They get used to perceiving abstract things instead of drawing conclusions based on concrete facts.

Adolescent children's attitude to work changes a lot. They try to do quality work, putting their heart into every job. Music is a field that is perceived mainly through mental work, and they now reach the level where they can make their own thoughts from the ideological content of musical works.

They absorb a number of norms related to moral education. Especially through songs about work, they get information about the work of people who are engaged in other professions. In particular, they will learn about the work of farmers, the profession of hairdressers, drivers and other professions. His love for teaching profession is growing.

Pupils will sing samples of songs about mothers and sisters on the occasion of March 8. Through these songs, it allows us to deeply feel the need to treat women with dignity and respect.

In grades 5-7, students gain a deeper understanding of the concepts of Motherland, Motherland, and Motherland.

In the stories about the Motherland, they will learn about the beauty of the Uzbek land, fertile lands, garden meadows, velvety dirt filled with red tulips, muddy rivers, and fruits. They also develop aesthetic thinking. Especially when they sing about beauty, they realize that their voices should be beautiful and sweet enough to express that beauty.

Thus, it is important to study the psychological condition of students in the teenage years, to learn about the physiological and biological changes that occur in them, and to form their singing skills.

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